

A CALPHAD assessment of the Ga–In–Sn liquidus for designable low-melting liquid-metal coolants

Michael Bustamante¹, Kristina Lilova²

¹ Odinzen LLC, Houston, TX, United States

² Center for Materials of the Universe, School of Molecular Sciences, Arizona State University, P.O. Box 871604, Tempe, AZ 85287-1604, USA

Corresponding author: Michael Bustamante (michaelbusta@odinzen.io)

Abstract

Gallium-based liquid metals combine high thermal conductivity with melting temperatures near room temperature, making the Ga–In–Sn system attractive candidate for thermal management of high heat flux electronics. Designing application specific coolants requires an accurate thermodynamic description of the liquidus surface across the full composition range. We report a CALPHAD assessment of the Ga–In–Sn liquidus calculated by combining optimized descriptions of the Ga–In, Ga–Sn, and In–Sn binary systems through the Muggianu extrapolation and introducing a single symmetric ternary interaction parameter. The Ga–Sn liquid is reassessed using experimental mixing enthalpies measured by quantitative differential thermal analysis with a root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) of 41 J/mol. The calculation workflow is confirmed against the Pb–Sn eutectic; the calculated invariant deviates by 1.1 °C and 0.1 wt% from accepted values. The resulting thermodynamic model reproduces the binary eutectics within 2 °C of the expected values and predicts the ternary eutectic at 9.85 °C. Binary extrapolation without a ternary interaction already predicts the eutectic within 1.9 °C, indicating that binary interactions account for most of the excess Gibbs energy of the ternary liquid. The resulting liquidus surface provides a computational framework for designing Ga–In–Sn alloys with application specific melting temperatures. The complete thermodynamic database, pycalphad scripts, and calculated composition grids are released to enable independent validation, reuse, and future refinement of the assessment.

Keywords: CALPHAD; Ga–In–Sn; Galinstan; liquidus projection; liquid-metal coolant; Muggianu extrapolation

1. Introduction

Modern electronics present an increasingly complicated thermal management challenge. From high-performance processors to artificial intelligence accelerators in data centres, chip heat fluxes now reach and exceed 100 W/cm², a regime where air cooling is no longer viable and even water-cooled systems approach their practical limits[1,2].

Gallium-based liquid metals offer a route through this constraint by combining high thermal conductivity, low vapour pressure, and melting temperatures at or below room temperature. The Ga–In–Sn alloy marketed as Galinstan combines a liquidus near room temperature with a thermal conductivity of 16.5 W/(m·K) at 25 °C[3], independently confirmed at values between 16 and 24 W/(m·K) over the liquid range by Lourenco et al.[4] and Zhang et al.[5], roughly 25 times that of water, and a vapour pressure negligible relative to mercury[5]. A Ga–In–Sn coolant circulating through a microchannel heat exchanger can therefore remove heat from a chip surface far more efficiently than any water-based alternative while remaining fully liquid at ambient temperature, making it a promising candidate for the next generation of electronics cooling.

Realizing this potential, however, requires understanding how the liquidus temperature varies with composition. A liquid-metal coolant must remain fully liquid over its entire operating temperature range, yet the lowest-liquidus compositions are often indium-rich and therefore associated with higher material costs. Selecting from a limited catalogue of established alloy compositions constrains the design space available to engineers. A reliable thermodynamic description of the liquidus surface removes that constraint. For any candidate composition, the model returns the liquidus onset temperature, enabling systematic optimization of both material cost and operating temperature margin across the full composition space.

The CALPHAD method provides a thermodynamic description by parameterizing the Gibbs energy of each phase as a function of composition and temperature and calculating phase equilibria by minimization [6]. Thermodynamic descriptions of the Ga–In and In–Sn liquid phases have previously been reported [7,8]. The available Ga–Sn assessment [9] predates the calorimetric data of Zivkovic et al.[10] and does not adequately describe those data. Accordingly, the Ga–Sn binary liquid was re-evaluated in this work. The ternary eutectic was experimentally measured by Evans and Prince [11], but a validated thermodynamic assessment of the Ga–In–Sn liquid phase, together with the corresponding database and optimization files, has not previously been made publicly available. The only prior computational treatment of this system identified in the present literature survey is a preprint by Pal et al. [12], who used FactSage 7.3 to design Sn-rich liquid-metal composite alloys for lead-free solder applications. In that work, the liquidus projection and selected vertical sections were used to identify compositions in which a liquid Ga–In–Sn eutectic remains embedded within a solid β -Sn matrix at room temperature. The Evans and Prince eutectic was reproduced by introducing ternary interaction parameters for both the liquid phase and the β -Sn solid solution. However, neither the optimized parameters nor the thermodynamic database were reported, precluding independent validation or reuse of the assessment. In the present work, the Ga–In–Sn system is reassessed independently using pycalphad [13]. The resulting description reproduces the available experimental data using a single ternary interaction parameter in the liquid phase, while all thermodynamic parameters, database files, and optimization

scripts are released to enable complete reproducibility. To our knowledge, this is the first openly available CALPHAD description of the Ga–In–Sn liquidus developed specifically for computational design of low-melting liquid-metal coolants.

A distinction should also be made between the equilibrium eutectic temperature and the freezing behavior of commercial Galinstan. The melting temperature of Galinstan is near $-19\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas the thermodynamic ternary eutectic lies at $10.7 \pm 0.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [11]. Differential scanning calorimetry and rheological measurements show melting on heating around $10\text{--}11\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [14] consistent with [11]. Freezing on cooling, however, occurs near $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a hysteresis of approximately $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ attributed to substantial supercooling [14]. The lower temperature therefore reflects a kinetic delay in nucleation rather than a thermodynamic depression of the melting point. The present assessment addresses the equilibrium liquidus.

2. Methodology

The molar Gibbs energy of each phase is written as the sum of a reference term from the pure elements, an ideal mixing term, and an excess term. Pure-element reference and fusion data are taken from the SGTE compilation of Dinsdale [15]. The excess Gibbs energy of the liquid in each binary subsystem is represented by a Redlich–Kister polynomial [16],

$$G^E = x_i x_j \sum_k {}^kL_{i,j} (x_i - x_j)^k,$$

with temperature-dependent interaction coefficients ${}^kL = a + bT$. The ternary liquid is extrapolated from the three binaries by the Muggianu symmetric geometric model [17], to which at most one ternary interaction parameter is added. All equilibria were evaluated with the open-source pycalphad package [13] by global Gibbs energy minimization. Liquidus temperatures and invariant reactions were determined by evaluating equilibrium at a composition step of 0.005 mole fraction and a temperature step of $0.25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The eutectic composition and temperature were determined from the minimum calculated liquidus temperature within the search region. Because no interpolation is performed between sampled points, all reported invariant temperatures have an uncertainty of $\pm 0.125\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The Ga–In and In–Sn liquid descriptions are taken from the published assessments of Rugg and Chart [7] and David et al. [8] and the Ga–Sn liquid was reassessed in the present assessment (Section 3.2). This assessment covers the liquid phase only. Solid phases are treated as pure substances using SGTE unary Gibbs energies [15] and no excess parameters are introduced for any solid. No intermetallic compounds have been reported in the Ga–In–Sn system that would intersect the liquidus in the Ga-rich composition range examined here. The assessment is therefore restricted to the liquid phase and the liquidus surface. Below the liquidus, phase equilibria are described only to the extent required for the binary In–Sn intermediate phases [8] to reproduce the liquidus boundaries. The solid-phase descriptions

for In–Sn (the β tI2, γ hP5, and BCT_A5 phases) are taken from [8], the terminal phases for pure Ga (orthorhombic), pure In (face-centred tetragonal), and pure Sn (BCT_A5, the same beta-tin structure used in the In–Sn description) use the SGTE unary functions from [15].

3. Binary subsystems

The liquid-phase Redlich–Kister parameters used in the assessment are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Liquid-phase Redlich–Kister interaction parameters. The In–Sn solid phases follow the David et al. assessment [8]; the Ga–Sn and ternary parameters were fitted in the present assessment.

System	Parameter	Value (J/mol)	Source
Ga–In (liquid)	0L	$4345 + 1.700 \cdot T$	[7]
	1L	$-146 + 0.464 \cdot T$	[7]
	2L	248	[7]
Ga–Sn (liquid)	0L	3744	present assessment (data [10])
	1L	643	present assessment (data: [10])
	2L	-413	present assessment (data: [10])
In–Sn (liquid)	0L	$-769 - 0.1312 \cdot T$	[8]
	1L	$-119 - 0.3902 \cdot T$	[8]
Ga–In–Sn (liquid)	L (;0 only)	-8000	present assessment (T_{eut} : [10])

3.1. Ga–In and In–Sn

The Ga–In liquid data is taken from Rugg and Chart [7]. It places the Ga–In eutectic at 15.9 °C and 14.5 at% In (Figure 1), in good agreement with the assessed value of 16.0 °C and 14.2 at% In [7].

Figure 1. Calculated Ga–In phase diagram from the Rugg and Chart liquid model [7]; the assessed eutectic is recovered within about 0.5 °C.

The In–Sn description of David et al. [8] includes the β and γ intermediate compounds (tetragonal tI2 and hexagonal hP5 Pearson structures) which determine the In-rich liquidus and set the deep eutectic. These phases are included to correctly reproduce the In–Sn binary liquidus edge of the ternary surface (Figure 2). Both beta and gamma phases are not expected to be stable within the Ga-rich composition range (Table 4). The description reproduces the In–Sn eutectic at 119.9 °C and 48.0 at% Sn, which is very similar to the previously reported values of 120 °C and 48.3 at% Sn [3]. The melting point of the pure gallium is determined as 29.9 °C in the SGTE functions, consistent with the accepted 29.8 °C [5].

Figure 2. Calculated In–Sn phase diagram from the David et al. assessment [8], showing the β (tI2) and γ (hP5) intermediate phases; eutectic 119.9 °C at 48 at% Sn.

3.2. Ga–Sn reassessment

The Ga–Sn binary liquid has been initially assessed by Anderson and Ansara [9] however, that assessment predates the enthalpy of mixing measurements Zivkovic et al. [10] and uses temperature dependent interaction parameters optimized to earlier phase boundary data. As a result, the extrapolated description is inconsistent with the Zivkovic et al. dataset. To maintain a consistent experimentally derived parameters across all three binaries, the liquid excess Gibbs energy was calculated from the differential thermal analysis data (DTA) [10]. Živković et al. performed two DTA measurements of the same sample. During the first measurements, gallium melted at the expected temperature of 29.8 °C and tin at 232 °C. The mixing enthalpy was calculated from the combined DTA peak area by subtracting the known fusion enthalpies of the pure components [10]. Since a single enthalpy of mixing value was measured at one temperature, the available data do not constrain a temperature-dependent interaction parameter. ($bT = 0$). This simplification does not account for any temperature dependence of the mixing behavior and likely contributes to the remaining 2.1 °C deviation between the calculated and assessed binary eutectic temperatures. The Redlich-Kister parameters were obtained by nonlinear least-squares fitting (Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, `scipy.optimize.curve_fit`) to the seven enthalpy of mixing [10]. The fit gives the parameters listed in Table 1 with a root-mean-square deviation of 41 J/mol (Figure 3). The resulting description places the Ga–Sn eutectic

at 21.1 °C and 7.2 at% Sn (Figure 4), against the assessed 19 °C and 8.5 at% Sn [9]. The deviations of 2.1 °C in temperature and 1.3 at% Sn in composition are the largest among the three binary subsystems. As discussed in Section 7, the sensitivity of the ternary eutectic temperature to the Ga–Sn interaction parameter (3.5 °C per 1000 J/mol perturbation of ${}^{\circ}L$) indicates that this binary is the dominant source of systematic uncertainty in the predicted ternary eutectic.

Figure 3. Excess enthalpy of mixing of the Ga–Sn liquid. Solid line: calculated from the fitted Redlich–Kister parameters (${}^{\circ}L = 3744$, ${}^1L = 643$, ${}^2L = -413$ J/mol, temperature-independent). Open squares: experimental mixing enthalpies from Zivkovic et al. [10] by quantitative differential thermal analysis (Table 3 of that work). The dashed vertical line marks the Ga–Sn eutectic composition (7.2 at% Sn); the root mean square deviation of the fit is 41 J/mol.

Figure 4. Ga–Sn phase diagram reassessment using the experimentally measured mixing enthalpies [10]; eutectic 21.1 °C at 7.2 at% Sn.

4. Ternary assessment

Without a ternary interaction parameter, Muggianu extrapolation of the three optimized liquid binary systems places the Ga–In–Sn eutectic at 12.6 °C near Ga81–In12–Sn7 (at%), which is within 1.9 °C of the experimental value. This close agreement indicates that the binary interactions account for most of the excess Gibbs energy of the ternary liquid. The remaining discrepancy is adequately described by a single symmetric ternary interaction parameter, consistent with the relatively small positive excess Gibbs energies of the Ga–In and Ga–Sn binary liquids (+4345 and +3744 J/mol, respectively), which together suggest nearly ideal mixing behavior of the ternary liquid. A single symmetric ternary interaction parameter, $L(\text{Ga}, \text{In}, \text{Sn}) = -8000$ J/mol, was fitted to the eutectic temperature of Evans and Prince [11]. The ternary interaction is represented by the zeroth-order Muggianu coefficient, (symmetric $x_{\text{Ga}}x_{\text{In}}x_{\text{Sn}}^0L$ term) and the asymmetric first- and second-order coefficients are set to zero. The optimized ternary parameter is negative, partially compensating the positive excess Gibbs energies of the binary liquid phases and indicating a modest stabilization of the ternary liquid relative to binary extrapolation. With this single parameter, and every binary description unchanged, the calculated eutectic shifts within the ± 0.3 °C uncertainty of the Evans and Prince value or 10.4 °C. This residual gap indicates that $L = -8000$ J/mol slightly overcorrects; a less negative parameter would narrow the discrepancy, but simultaneous fitting to liquidus compositions (rather than the eutectic temperature alone) is the appropriate route to a more accurate description. The

experimental uncertainty of the eutectic temperature corresponds to approximately ± 1200 J/mol of the optimized ternary interaction parameter, based on the sensitivity of less than 0.5 °C per 1000 J/mol shown in Table 3.

No activity measurements for the liquid ternary were identified in CALPHAD literature, the Hultgren compilation [18], the NIST WebBook, or Landolt-Börnstein reference collection for physical and chemical data. The mixing enthalpies of the ternary eutectic composition measured by oxidative solution calorimetry [19] are compared with the Muggianu extrapolation (Section 5). The single ternary interaction parameter was optimized solely to reproduce the eutectic temperature; consequently, the eutectic composition remains under constrained. Additional composition dependent liquidus data are required to uniquely determine the invariant composition. As a result, the calculated composition, Ga71–In18–Sn11 (at%), is more indium-rich than the reported value of Ga76–In14–Sn10 (at%) [10]. This discrepancy is the principal limitation of the present description and is discussed further in Section 7.

5. Validation

Before assessing the Ga–In–Sn system, the computational workflow was verified by reproducing the published Pb–Sn binary phase diagram using the independently developed thermodynamic database distributed with pycalphad. The Pb–Sn eutectic, calculated from the assessment of Ngai and Chang [20] as distributed with pycalphad, is reproduced at 181.9 °C and 62.0 wt% Sn (Figure 5) consistent with the accepted 183.0 °C and 61.9 wt% Sn (Figure 5). This confirms that the workflow can reproduce a known invariant from externally supplied parameters, with no error introduced in the equilibrium search. Calculated invariants for the control system, the three binaries, and the ternary are listed in Table 2.

Figure 5. Calculated Pb–Sn phase diagram (validation). The eutectic is reproduced to within 1.1 °C and 0.1 wt% of the accepted value [20].

Table 2. Calculated invariants compared with assessed or measured reference values. The control Pb–Sn phase diagram and the three binary eutectics are reproduced to within 2 °C. The ternary eutectic temperature is calculated with and without a ternary interaction parameter. The calculated ternary eutectic composition (last row) is more indium-rich than the measured value (Section 7).

System	Invariant	This work	Reference	Source
Pb–Sn (control)	eutectic T composition	181.9 °C 74.0 at% Sn	183.0 °C 74.0 at% Sn	[20]
Ga (pure)	melting point	29.9 °C	29.8 °C	[15]
Ga–In	eutectic T composition	15.9 °C 14.5 at% In	16.0 °C 14.2 at% In	[7]
Ga–Sn	eutectic T composition	21.1 °C 7.2 at% Sn	19 °C 8.5 at% Sn	[10]
In–Sn	eutectic T composition	119.9 °C 48.0 at% Sn	120 °C 48.3 at% Sn	[8]
Ga–In–Sn (no ternary term)	eutectic T	12.6 °C	N/A	present assessment
Ga–In–Sn (ternary term)	eutectic T composition	9.85 °C Ga71–In18– Sn11 at%	10.7 ± 0.3 °C Ga76–In14–Sn10 at%	[11]

The thermodynamic description of the ternary liquid is independently supported by calorimetric measurements. Bustamante et al. [19] measured the mixing enthalpy of the Ga–In–Sn eutectic composition (Ga78.2–In14.8–Sn7.0, at%) at 25 °C by oxidative solution calorimetry as $\Delta H_{\text{mix}} = +0.75 \pm 5.62$ kJ/mol. The Muggianu extrapolation of the three binary descriptions at this composition predicts +0.71 kJ/mol, which is within the measurement uncertainty. This close agreement indicates that the binary Redlich–Kister parameters account for most of the excess Gibbs energy of the ternary liquid, consistent with the relatively small excess Gibbs energies of the Ga-containing binary liquids. The ternary parameter $L(\text{Ga},\text{In},\text{Sn})$ adjusts the liquidus surface without modifying the enthalpy of mixing.

6. Results

The calculated Ga–In–Sn liquidus projection calculated with a ternary interaction parameter is shown on Figure 6. Isotherms converge on the eutectic at 9.85 °C in the gallium-rich corner, 0.85 °C below the Evans and Prince measurement [11]. Figure 7 shows the extrapolated Muggianu surface, calculated with no ternary parameter for a comparison. The single ternary parameter lowers the eutectic by 2.75 °C while leaving the binary liquidus boundaries unchanged. Figure 8 shows a vertical section at a constant indium content of 18 at% In passing through the calculated eutectic composition Ga71–In18–Sn11 (at%). The liquidus minimum at 9.6 °C near 10.9 at.% Sn is within 0.25 °C of the eutectic temperature, consistent with the 0.25 °C temperature resolution of the equilibrium calculations. Differential scanning calorimetry of commercial Galinstan [12] show melting onset between 10 and 11 °C, in good agreement with the calculated liquidus temperature 9.85 °C.

Figure 6. Ga–In–Sn liquidus projection calculated with a ternary interaction parameter. Liquidus isotherms across the composition triangle, with the eutectic at 9.85 °C in the gallium-rich corner (Evans and Prince: 10.7 ± 0.3 °C [11]).

with In-Sn intermediate phases β and γ (David et al. 2004)

Figure 7. Ga–In–Sn liquidus (Muggianu extrapolation, no ternary interaction parameter), including the In–Sn intermediate phases. The eutectic is at 12.6 °C.

Figure 8. Calculated liquidus isopleth (vertical section) at constant 18 at% In, as a function of $x(\text{Sn})$. The section is passing through the calculated eutectic composition (Ga71-In18-Sn11 at%). The liquidus minimum at 9.6 °C near 10.9 at% Sn is within 0.25 °C of the eutectic temperature, consistent with the 0.25 °C temperature resolution of the equilibrium calculations

7. Discussion

The assessment uses three published binary descriptions, one Ga–Sn reassessment phase diagram based on enthalpy of mixing data [10], and one ternary parameter fitted to a single experimentally measured value (Zivkovic et al. [10]). The reliability of the assessment is demonstrated by the reproduction of the Pb–Sn validation system, the agreement of the binary assessments with experimental data (Table 2), and the relatively small ternary interaction parameter required to reproduce the measured eutectic temperature. Table 3 quantifies the sensitivity of the calculated eutectic to $\pm 1000 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$ perturbations of each binary zeroth order interaction parameter and the ternary interaction parameter. The Ga–In binary system has the largest temperature shift by up to 6.5 °C per 1000 J/mol, followed by the Ga–Sn binary with shifts of up to 4.0 °C per 1000 J/mol and the In–Sn binary with less than 0.5 °C per 1000 J/mol. The temperature shift is asymmetric with respect to positive and negative perturbations, reflecting the nonlinear curvature of the liquidus surface near the eutectic. The sensitivity of the gallium mole fraction follows the same pattern as the temperature shift.

The small local sensitivity reflects the curvature of the liquidus surface near the fitted point and should not be interpreted as evidence that the ternary interaction is

unimportant: removing L entirely shifts the eutectic by 2.75 °C, from 12.6 °C to 9.85 °C. The values reported as < 0.5 °C in Table 3 are within the 0.5 °C temperature increment used in the eutectic calculation. Among the binary parameters, the Ga–In interaction is the most promising target for further refinement. A more accurate Ga–In liquid description, based on a larger experimental dataset, would be expected to reduce the uncertainty in the ternary eutectic temperature more effectively than comparable improvements to the other parameters.

Table 3. Sensitivity of the calculated eutectic to ± 1000 J/mol perturbations of each binary zeroth order liquid interaction parameter and of the ternary L. Values are shifts in eutectic temperature (dT) and Ga mole fraction (dx_{Ga}) relative to the baseline (Table 2). The asymmetry between positive and negative perturbations reflects the nonlinear dependence of the eutectic temperature on the binary parameters near the invariant point. Entries marked < 0.5 indicate shifts smaller than the 0.5 °C temperature step used in the eutectic search, which cannot be resolved as non-zero in the discrete search output.

Parameter perturbed	dT +1000 (°C)	dT -1000 (°C)	dx_{Ga} +1000	dx_{Ga} -1000
Ga–In ⁰ L	+5.0	-6.5	+0.10	-0.08
Ga–Sn ⁰ L	+3.5	-4.0	+0.07	-0.05
In–Sn ⁰ L	< 0.5	< 0.5	< 0.02	< 0.02
L(Ga,In,Sn)	< 0.5	< 0.5	< 0.02	< 0.02

The principal limitation is that a single ternary parameter, fitted to the eutectic temperature, does not also reproduce the eutectic composition. The calculated invariant lies at Ga71–In18–Sn11 (at%), more indium-rich than the measured Ga76–In14–Sn10 (at%). This discrepancy has two contributing sources. First, the Ga–Sn binary reassessment reproduces within 2.1 °C and 1.3 at% Sn of the literature values [9]. As shown by the sensitivity analysis, the Ga–Sn interaction shifts the ternary eutectic by up to 4.0 °C per 1000 J/mol which propagates into the ternary prediction. Second, using a single symmetric ternary interaction parameter cannot simultaneously correct both the temperature and the location of the ternary invariant.

The model is therefore accurate for the eutectic temperature and the overall liquidus topology, but not for the invariant composition. Evaluating the model at the measured eutectic composition (Ga76In14Sn10, at.%) gives a liquidus temperature of 11.6 °C, which is 1.2 °C above the calculated eutectic temperature. This offset is assigned as the liquidus uncertainty because that composition lies on the indium-rich side of the calculated eutectic (Table 4). The compositions located well into the Ga-rich corner (Table 4) are correspondingly less affected. Evans and Prince [11] reported the liquidus surface as a set of graphical isotherms (their Figure 3) rather than tabulated temperatures, so a quantitative isopleth comparison requires digitization of that figure. We therefore defer that comparison

to the composition-accurate optimization described below, where the digitized isotherms provide the natural fitting targets. Capturing both the temperature and composition of the invariant would require additional ternary parameters fitted simultaneously to the liquidus across composition rather than to the eutectic alone. A natural next step is to optimize the liquid and β -Sn ternary interaction parameters simultaneously against the digitized Evans and Prince liquidus isotherms. Formal uncertainty quantification could then be performed using the Bayesian capabilities of ESPEI [21,22] to propagate parameter uncertainty into confidence intervals on the calculated liquidus surface.

Table 4. Calculated liquidus temperatures for selected Ga–In–Sn compositions in the gallium-rich corner. The eutectic (9.85 °C, Ga71–In18–Sn11 at%) is the minimum on the liquidus surface; all other compositions lie above it. Liquidus temperatures carry a discretization uncertainty of ± 0.125 °C from the 0.25 °C temperature step used in the eutectic calculation.

Composition (at%)	Ga	In	Sn	T _{liq} (°C)
Ga77–In14–Sn9 (nominal Galinstan)	77.2	14.3	8.5	12.9
Ga81–In10–Sn9 (Ga-rich variant)	81.1	10.3	8.6	13.9
Ga71–In18–Sn11 (In-rich variant)	71.4	18.1	10.5	10.9
Ga87–In7–Sn6 (high-Ga)	87.0	6.6	6.4	17.9

8. Application: a designable melting range

Representing the liquidus surface as a continuous function of composition enables computational alloy design by allowing compositions to be selected for a specified liquidus temperature. Table 4 illustrates this design space using four representative compositions in the Ga-rich region. Commercial Galinstan (Ga77.2–In14.3–Sn8.5 at%) has a calculated liquidus of 9.85 °C and therefore remains fully liquid at ambient temperature while retaining a thermal margin of approximately 7–12 °C above its minimum operating temperature before the onset of solidification. Reducing indium (Ga81–In10–Sn9) raises the liquidus to 13.9 °C thus reducing the thermal margin before solidification onset. Increasing the indium content (Ga71.4–In18.1–Sn10.5 at%) lowers the calculated liquidus to 10.9 °C, approaching the eutectic from the indium-rich side. Because this composition lies close to the eutectic, where the uncertainty discussed in Section 7 is largest, its calculated liquidus should be regarded as approximate until a composition-constrained assessment becomes available. Increasing gallium well beyond the eutectic (Ga87–In7–Sn6) raises the liquidus to 17.9 °C, demonstrating that the eutectic represents the minimum of the liquidus surface and that any displacement from it increases the melting onset.

Collectively, these examples span a liquidus range of approximately 7 °C and illustrate the sensitivity of the liquidus temperature to composition in the Ga-rich region.

The calculated liquidus surface defines the equilibrium onset of solidification. In practice, Ga–In–Sn alloys close to the eutectic, including commercial Galinstan, can undergo substantial supercooling before nucleation of the solid phase [12]. The liquidus temperatures reported here therefore represent thermodynamic equilibrium, whereas the observed freezing temperature depends on nucleation kinetics. Any strategy intended to reduce undercooling should promote nucleation closer to the equilibrium liquidus temperature.

9. Conclusion

Three binary liquid descriptions combined through the Muggianu extrapolation and supplemented by a single symmetric ternary interaction provide a thermodynamic description of the Ga–In–Sn liquidus with a minimal number of adjustable parameters. The Muggianu surface without any ternary term predicts the ternary eutectic within 1.9 °C of the experimental value, demonstrating that the binary interactions account for most of the excess Gibbs energy of the ternary liquid. Introducing a single negative ternary interaction parameter reproduces the experimental eutectic temperature while leaving the optimized binary descriptions unchanged.

The present assessment accurately describes the equilibrium liquidus temperature and the overall topology of the liquidus surface but does not uniquely constrain the eutectic composition. This limitation arises because the ternary interaction parameter was optimized only against the eutectic temperature, while the available liquidus isotherms remain available only in graphical form. A more complete assessment will require simultaneous optimization against digitized liquidus data across the composition triangle, together with formal uncertainty quantification.

Despite this limitation, the assessment provides a practical thermodynamic framework for computational design of Ga–In–Sn liquid-metal coolants. By representing the liquidus as a continuous function of composition, it enables alloy compositions to be selected for a specified liquidus temperature rather than from a limited set of established formulations. The complete thermodynamic database, pycalphad scripts, and calculated composition grids are released with this work to enable independent validation, reuse, and future refinement of the assessment.

Data availability

The thermodynamic databases (GaInSn.tdb, GaInSn_fitted.tdb, InSn_David2004.tdb), the pycalphad calculation and plotting scripts, and the liquidus composition meshes as CSV files that reproduce the figures and tables are provided as supplementary material with this article. They are deposited Zenodo and Git Hub at <https://zenodo.org/records/21038087>. Every parameter trace to a cited assessment or to the fit described here.

CRedit author statement

Michael E. Bustamante: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing (original draft), Writing (review and editing), Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition. Kristina Lilova: Writing (review and editing), Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Use of AI-assisted tools

During the preparation of this manuscript the authors used Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic) to assist with development of the pycalphad calculation scripts, figure generation code, and prose drafting. AI assistance was limited to text editing and code generation; all thermodynamic parameters, literature sources, and scientific conclusions were determined and verified by the authors. The authors take full responsibility for the content of this publication.

References

- [1] P.J. Shamberger, N.M. Bruno, Review of metallic phase change materials for high heat flux transient thermal management applications, *Applied Energy* 258 (2020) 113955. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113955>.
- [2] A. Miner, U. Ghoshal, Cooling of high-power-density microdevices using liquid metal coolants, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 85 (2004) 506–508. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1772862>.
- [3] Y. Plevachuk, V. Sklyarchuk, S. Eckert, G. Gerbeth, R. Novakovic, Thermophysical Properties of the Liquid Ga–In–Sn Eutectic Alloy, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 59 (2014) 757–763. <https://doi.org/10.1021/je400882q>.
- [4] M.J.V. Lourenço, M. Alves, J.M. Serra, C.A. Nieto de Castro, M.H. Buschmann, The Thermal Conductivity of Near-Eutectic Galinstan (Ga_{68.4}In_{21.5}Sn₁₀) Molten Alloy, *Int J Thermophys* 45 (2023) 6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10765-023-03293-0>.
- [5] M. Zhang, P. Liao, Y. Cao, T. Sun, X. Liu, Gallium-Based Liquid Metals: From Fundamental Properties to State-of-the-Art Applications, *Nanomaterials* 16 (2026) 198. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano16030198>.
- [6] H.L. Lukas, S.G. Fries, B. Sundman, *Computational thermodynamics: the CALPHAD method*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge; New York, 2007.
- [7] B.C. Rugg, T.G. Chart, A critical assessment of thermodynamic and phase diagram data for the gallium-indium system, *Calphad* 14 (1990) 115–123. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916\(90\)90013-P](https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916(90)90013-P).
- [8] N. David, K. El Aissaoui, J.M. Fiorani, J. Hertz, M. Vilasi, Thermodynamic optimization of the In–Pb–Sn system based on new evaluations of the binary borders

- In-Pb and In-Sn, *Thermochimica Acta* 413 (2004) 127–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2003.10.020>.
- [9] T.J. Anderson, I. Ansara, The Ga-Sn (gallium-tin) system, *JPE* 13 (1992) 181–189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02667485>.
- [10] D. Zivkovic, D. Manasijevic, Z. Zivkovic, Thermodynamic study of Ga-Sn and Ga-Zn systems using quantitative differential thermal analysis, *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry* 74 (2003) 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026373602352>.
- [11] D.S. Evans, A. Prince, Thermal analysis of Ga-In-Sn system, *Metal Science* 12 (1978) 411–414. <https://doi.org/10.1179/030634578790434025>.
- [12] V. Pal, R. Das, R. Ambekhar, A. Kumar, J. Vasavada, B. Kumar, S.K. Kar, S. Sarkar, M. Palit, A.K. Roy, M. Paliwal, K. Biswas, S. Bhoumik, S. Mishra, C. Bakli, C.S. Tiwary, Liquid-phase reinforced Metal matrix (LMM) composite with non-intuitive properties, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2002.03151>.
- [13] R. Otis, Z.-K. Liu, pycalphad: CALPHAD-based Computational Thermodynamics in Python, *Journal of Open Research Software* 5 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.140>.
- [14] A. Koh, W. Hwang, P. Y. Zavalij, S. Chun, G. Slipher, R. Mrozek, Solidification and melting phase change behavior of eutectic gallium-indium-tin, *Materialia* 8 (2019) 100512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtla.2019.100512>.
- [15] A.T. Dinsdale, SGTE data for pure elements, *Calphad* 15 (1991) 317–425. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916\(91\)90030-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916(91)90030-N).
- [16] O. Redlich, A.T. Kister, Algebraic Representation of Thermodynamic Properties and the Classification of Solutions, *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 40 (1948) 345–348. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie50458a036>.
- [17] Y.-M. Muggianu, M. Gambino, J.-P. Bros, Enthalpies de formation des alliages liquides bismuth-étain-gallium à 723 k. Choix d’une représentation analytique des grandeurs d’excès intégrales et partielles de mélange, *J. Chim. Phys.* 72 (1975) 83–88. <https://doi.org/10.1051/jcp/1975720083>.
- [18] R. Hultgren, Selected values of the thermodynamic properties of binary alloys, American Society for Metals, Metals Park, Ohio, 1973.
- [19] M. Bustamante, K. Lilova, A. Navrotsky, J.-P. Harvey, K. Oishi, Enthalpies of mixing for alloys liquid below room temperature determined by oxidative solution calorimetry, *J Therm Anal Calorim* 149 (2024) 4817–4826. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-024-13035-5>.
- [20] T. Leo Ngai, Y. Austin Chang, A thermodynamic analysis of the PbSn system and the calculation of the PbSn phase diagram, *Calphad* 5 (1981) 267–276. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916\(81\)90009-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0364-5916(81)90009-2).
- [21] B. Bocklund, R. Otis, A. Egorov, A. Obaied, I. Roslyakova, Z.-K. Liu, ESPEI for efficient thermodynamic database development, modification, and uncertainty quantification: application to Cu–Mg, *MRS Communications* 9 (2019) 618–627. <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrc.2019.59>.
- [22] R.A. Otis, Z.-K. Liu, High-Throughput Thermodynamic Modeling and Uncertainty Quantification for ICME, *JOM* 69 (2017) 886–892. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-017-2318-6>.